

Alternative Layouts for Grid Questions in PC and Mobile Web Surveys: An Experimental Evaluation Using Response Quality Indicators and Survey Estimates

T-Tests

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T-tests are the basis for determining statistical significance of the relative differences.

1 T-tests for RQIs

1.1 Differences in RQIs between a specific layout and the five-layout average

Table 1: Comparing breakoffs to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.107					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.478	490	0.633	-0.006	-0.03	0.02
	SP	3.45	427	0.001	0.063	0.03	0.1
Scrolling	PC	0.746	508	0.456	0.011	-0.02	0.04
	SP	4.206	439	0	0.078	0.04	0.11
Unfolding	PC	-0.389	509	0.698	-0.005	-0.03	0.02
	SP	3.613	407	0	0.068	0.03	0.11
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.676	502	0.499	-0.009	-0.04	0.02
	SP	4.832	434	0	0.093	0.06	0.13
Paging	PC	0.659	496	0.51	0.009	-0.02	0.04
	SP	6.375	412	0	0.134	0.09	0.18

Table 2: Comparing breakoffs to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.194					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-6.881	490	0	-0.093	-0.12	-0.07
	SP	-1.34	427	0.181	-0.024	-0.06	0.01
Scrolling	PC	-5.341	508	0	-0.076	-0.1	-0.05
	SP	-0.492	439	0.623	-0.009	-0.05	0.03

Unfolding	PC	-6.878	509	0	-0.092	-0.12	-0.07
	SP	-1.008	407	0.314	-0.019	-0.06	0.02
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-7.234	502	0	-0.096	-0.12	-0.07
	SP	0.299	434	0.765	0.006	-0.03	0.04
Paging	PC	-5.384	496	0	-0.078	-0.11	-0.05
	SP	2.246	412	0.025	0.047	0.01	0.09

Table 3: Comparing item nonresponse to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.0058					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.462	472	0.144	-0.00126	-0.003	0.0004
	SP	-0.534	409	0.594	-0.00058	-0.0027	0.0015
Scrolling	PC	-2.081	486	0.038	-0.00188	-0.0037	0.0001
	SP	-2.504	418	0.013	-0.00302	-0.0054	0.0006
Unfolding	PC	0.068	490	0.946	0.00012	-0.0033	0.0035
	SP	-4.812	390	0	-0.00272	-0.0038	0.0016
Horizontal scrolling	PC	2.986	486	0.003	0.00523	0.0018	0.0087
	SP	6.483	410	0	0.01302	0.0091	0.017
Paging	PC	-2.758	472	0.006	-0.00325	-0.0056	0.0009
	SP	-4.794	388	0	-0.00399	-0.0056	0.0024

Table 4: Comparing item nonresponse to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.0064					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-2.159	472	0.031	-0.00186	-0.0036	0.0002
	SP	-1.089	409	0.277	-0.00118	-0.0033	0.0009
Scrolling	PC	-2.744	486	0.006	-0.00248	-0.0043	0.0007
	SP	-3.002	418	0.003	-0.00362	-0.006	0.0012
Unfolding	PC	-0.278	490	0.781	-0.00048	-0.0039	0.0029
	SP	-5.872	390	0	-0.00332	-0.0044	0.0022
Horizontal scrolling	PC	2.644	486	0.008	0.00463	0.0012	0.0081
	SP	6.185	410	0	0.01242	0.0085	0.0164
Paging	PC	-3.267	472	0.001	-0.00385	-0.0062	0.0015
	SP	-5.516	388	0	-0.00459	-0.0062	-0.003

Table 5: Comparing straightlining to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.388					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	2.131	446	0.034	0.07394	0.0057	0.1421
	SP	2.575	372	0.01	0.10634	0.0251	0.1875
Scrolling	PC	0.564	459	0.573	0.01675	-0.0416	0.0751
	SP	-0.506	374	0.613	-0.01523	-0.0744	0.0439
Unfolding	PC	0.53	464	0.597	0.01605	-0.0435	0.0756
	SP	-0.81	360	0.418	-0.02462	-0.0844	0.0351
Horizontal scrolling	PC	0.523	459	0.601	0.01677	-0.0463	0.0798
	SP	0.351	363	0.726	0.01162	-0.0535	0.0768
Paging	PC	-4.614	456	0	-0.1062	-0.1514	-0.061
	SP	-2.472	333	0.014	-0.07188	-0.1291	0.0147

Table 6: Comparing straightlining to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.392					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	2.015	446	0.044	0.06994	0.0017	0.1381
	SP	2.478	372	0.014	0.10234	0.0211	0.1835
Scrolling	PC	0.429	459	0.668	0.01275	-0.0456	0.0711
	SP	-0.639	374	0.523	-0.01923	-0.0784	0.0399
Unfolding	PC	0.398	464	0.691	0.01205	-0.0475	0.0716
	SP	-0.942	360	0.347	-0.02862	-0.0884	0.0311
Horizontal scrolling	PC	0.398	459	0.691	0.01277	-0.0503	0.0758
	SP	0.23	363	0.818	0.00762	-0.0575	0.0728
Paging	PC	-4.787	456	0	-0.1102	-0.1554	-0.065
	SP	-2.609	333	0.009	-0.07588	-0.1331	0.0187

Table 7: Comparing extreme positive responses to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.0596					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	2.224	446	0.027	0.01066	0.0012	0.0201
	SP	3.825	372	0	0.02841	0.0138	0.043
Scrolling	PC	0.107	459	0.915	0.00046	-0.008	0.0089
	SP	2.435	374	0.015	0.01308	0.0025	0.0236
Unfolding	PC	-0.788	464	0.431	-0.00343	-0.012	0.0051
	SP	1.388	360	0.166	0.00773	-0.0032	0.0187
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-1.422	461	0.156	-0.00621	-0.0148	0.0024
	SP	0.718	364	0.473	0.00335	-0.0058	0.0125
Paging	PC	-0.974	456	0.331	-0.00359	-0.0108	0.0037
	SP	2.414	335	0.016	0.01732	0.0032	0.0314

Table 8: Comparing extreme positive responses to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.0694					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	0.179	446	0.858	0.00086	-0.0086	0.0103
	SP	2.506	372	0.013	0.01861	0.004	0.0332
Scrolling	PC	-2.172	459	0.03	-0.00934	-0.0178	0.0009
	SP	0.611	374	0.542	0.00328	-0.0073	0.0138
Unfolding	PC	-3.037	464	0.003	-0.01323	-0.0218	0.0047
	SP	-0.371	360	0.711	-0.00207	-0.013	0.0089
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-3.666	461	0	-0.01601	-0.0246	0.0074
	SP	-1.381	364	0.168	-0.00645	-0.0156	0.0027
Paging	PC	-3.632	456	0	-0.01339	-0.0206	0.0061
	SP	1.048	335	0.295	0.00752	-0.0066	0.0216

Table 9: Comparing extreme negative responses to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.1178					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	2.238	446	0.026	0.01361	0.0017	0.0256
	SP	3.178	372	0.002	0.02267	0.0086	0.0367
Scrolling	PC	-0.675	459	0.5	-0.00362	-0.0142	0.0069
	SP	-0.58	374	0.562	-0.00326	-0.0143	0.0078
Unfolding	PC	-0.686	464	0.493	-0.00371	-0.0144	0.0069
	SP	-0.762	360	0.447	-0.00492	-0.0176	0.0078
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-1.712	461	0.088	-0.009	-0.0193	0.0013
	SP	-3.03	364	0.003	-0.01513	-0.025	0.0053
Paging	PC	0.495	456	0.621	0.00285	-0.0085	0.0142
	SP	1.339	335	0.182	0.00913	-0.0043	0.0225

Table 10: Comparing extreme negative responses to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.1202					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	1.843	446	0.066	0.01121	-0.0007	0.0232
	SP	2.841	372	0.005	0.02027	0.0062	0.0343
Scrolling	PC	-1.122	459	0.262	-0.00602	-0.0166	0.0045
	SP	-1.006	374	0.315	-0.00566	-0.0167	0.0054
Unfolding	PC	-1.129	464	0.26	-0.00611	-0.0168	0.0045
	SP	-1.133	360	0.258	-0.00732	-0.02	0.0054
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-2.168	461	0.031	-0.0114	-0.0217	0.0011
	SP	-3.511	364	0.001	-0.01753	-0.0274	0.0077
Paging	PC	0.078	456	0.938	0.00045	-0.0109	0.0118
	SP	0.987	335	0.324	0.00673	-0.0067	0.0201

Table 11: Comparing midpoint responses to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.3424					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	0.646	446	0.518	0.00565	-0.0115	0.0228
	SP	-0.918	372	0.359	-0.00896	-0.0282	0.0102
Scrolling	PC	-0.129	459	0.898	-0.00116	-0.0188	0.0165
	SP	-1.687	374	0.092	-0.01495	-0.0324	0.0025
Unfolding	PC	1.014	464	0.311	0.00887	-0.0083	0.0261
	SP	-1.996	360	0.047	-0.01648	-0.0327	0.0002
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.951	461	0.342	-0.00765	-0.0235	0.0082
	SP	1.485	364	0.138	0.0138	-0.0045	0.0321
Paging	PC	-0.667	456	0.505	-0.00533	-0.021	0.0104
	SP	-2.376	335	0.018	-0.02257	-0.0413	0.0039

Table 12: Comparing midpoint responses to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.3328					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	1.744	446	0.082	0.01525	-0.0019	0.0324
	SP	0.065	372	0.948	0.00064	-0.0186	0.0198
Scrolling	PC	0.94	459	0.348	0.00844	-0.0092	0.0261
	SP	-0.604	374	0.546	-0.00535	-0.0228	0.0121
Unfolding	PC	2.111	464	0.035	0.01847	0.0013	0.0357
	SP	-0.833	360	0.405	-0.00688	-0.0231	0.0094
Horizontal scrolling	PC	0.242	461	0.809	0.00195	-0.0139	0.0178
	SP	2.518	364	0.012	0.0234	0.0051	0.0417
Paging	PC	0.535	456	0.593	0.00427	-0.0114	0.02
	SP	-1.365	335	0.173	-0.01297	-0.0317	0.0057

Table 13: Comparing concurrent multitasking to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.202					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.182	440	0.856	-0.004	-0.05	0.04
	SP	-2.82	354	0.005	-0.059	-0.1	-0.02
Scrolling	PC	-0.616	448	0.538	-0.013	-0.05	0.03
	SP	0.209	358	0.834	0.005	-0.04	0.05
Unfolding	PC	-0.937	457	0.349	-0.021	-0.07	0.02
	SP	-0.733	336	0.464	-0.019	-0.07	0.03
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.994	453	0.321	-0.02	-0.06	0.02
	SP	1.297	348	0.196	0.039	-0.02	0.1
Paging	PC	2.509	439	0.012	0.062	0.01	0.11
	SP	0.085	312	0.932	0.002	-0.05	0.05

Table 14: Comparing concurrent multitasking to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.194					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	0.181	440	0.856	0.004	-0.04	0.05
	SP	-2.439	354	0.015	-0.051	-0.09	-0.01
Scrolling	PC	-0.225	448	0.822	-0.005	-0.04	0.04
	SP	0.531	358	0.596	0.013	-0.04	0.06
Unfolding	PC	-0.584	457	0.559	-0.013	-0.06	0.03
	SP	-0.426	336	0.671	-0.011	-0.06	0.04
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.604	453	0.546	-0.012	-0.05	0.03
	SP	1.56	348	0.12	0.047	-0.01	0.11
Paging	PC	2.831	439	0.005	0.07	0.02	0.12
	SP	0.394	312	0.694	0.01	-0.04	0.06

Table 15: Comparing sequential multitasking to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.19					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.228	440	0.22	-0.032	-0.08	0.02
	SP	0.018	354	0.986	0	-0.05	0.05
Scrolling	PC	-1.746	448	0.082	-0.039	-0.08	0
	SP	-1.422	358	0.156	-0.031	-0.07	0.01
Unfolding	PC	0.951	457	0.342	0.025	-0.03	0.08
	SP	-0.997	336	0.319	-0.026	-0.08	0.03
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.484	453	0.629	-0.013	-0.07	0.04
	SP	0.42	348	0.675	0.013	-0.05	0.07
Paging	PC	1.68	439	0.094	0.051	-0.01	0.11
	SP	0.319	312	0.75	0.01	-0.05	0.07

Table 16: Comparing sequential multitasking to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.182					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.923	440	0.356	-0.024	-0.08	0.03
	SP	0.329	354	0.742	0.008	-0.04	0.06
Scrolling	PC	-1.389	448	0.166	-0.031	-0.08	0.01
	SP	-1.056	358	0.292	-0.023	-0.07	0.02
Unfolding	PC	1.255	457	0.21	0.033	-0.02	0.08
	SP	-0.692	336	0.489	-0.018	-0.07	0.03
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.187	453	0.852	-0.005	-0.06	0.05
	SP	0.682	348	0.495	0.021	-0.04	0.08
Paging	PC	1.942	439	0.053	0.059	0	0.12
	SP	0.57	312	0.569	0.018	-0.04	0.08

Table 17: Comparing grid duration to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 870.84					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-15.996	440	0	188.65613	-211.8354	165.4768
	SP	-13.341	354	0	207.85181	-238.4927	177.2109
Scrolling	PC	-7.493	448	0	109.47996	-138.1949	-80.765
	SP	-13.959	358	0	186.76597	-213.0788	160.4532
Unfolding	PC	-11.855	457	0	158.28862	-184.5272	132.0501
	SP	-11.749	336	0	-180.8216	-211.0957	150.5475
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-5.8	453	0	-86.38796	-115.6567	-57.1192
	SP	-3.853	347	0	-68.30417	-103.1683	-33.4401
Paging	PC	14.186	439	0	542.70231	467.5149	617.8898
	SP	13.256	313	0	454.92966	387.4059	522.4534

Table 18: Comparing grid duration to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 833.08					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-12.794	440	0	150.89613	-174.0754	127.7168
	SP	-10.917	354	0	170.09181	-200.7327	139.4509
Scrolling	PC	-4.909	448	0	-71.71996	-100.4349	-43.005
	SP	-11.137	358	0	149.00597	-175.3188	122.6932
Unfolding	PC	-9.027	457	0	120.52862	-146.7672	-94.2901
	SP	-9.295	336	0	-143.0616	-173.3357	112.7875
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-3.265	453	0.001	-48.62796	-77.8967	-19.3592
	SP	-1.723	347	0.086	-30.54417	-65.4083	4.3199
Paging	PC	15.173	439	0	580.46231	505.2749	655.6498
	SP	14.357	313	0	492.68966	425.1659	560.2134

Table 19: Comparing self-reported burden to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 1.786					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.413	440	0.68	-0.017	-0.1	0.06
	SP	-1.599	356	0.111	-0.072	-0.16	0.02
Scrolling	PC	-3.345	448	0.001	-0.134	-0.21	-0.06
	SP	-2.168	359	0.031	-0.102	-0.19	-0.01
Unfolding	PC	-2.777	457	0.006	-0.114	-0.19	-0.03
	SP	1.468	337	0.143	0.079	-0.03	0.18
Horizontal scrolling	PC	0.016	452	0.988	0.001	-0.08	0.08
	SP	0.025	348	0.98	0.001	-0.09	0.1
Paging	PC	5.511	441	0	0.263	0.17	0.36
	SP	6.085	314	0	0.334	0.23	0.44

Table 20: Comparing self-reported burden to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 1.832					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.563	440	0.119	-0.063	-0.14	0.02
	SP	-2.62	356	0.009	-0.118	-0.21	-0.03
Scrolling	PC	-4.495	448	0	-0.18	-0.26	-0.1
	SP	-3.15	359	0.002	-0.148	-0.24	-0.06
Unfolding	PC	-3.901	457	0	-0.16	-0.24	-0.08
	SP	0.611	337	0.541	0.033	-0.07	0.14
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-1.06	452	0.29	-0.045	-0.13	0.04
	SP	-0.931	348	0.353	-0.045	-0.14	0.05
Paging	PC	4.548	441	0	0.217	0.12	0.31
	SP	5.247	314	0	0.288	0.18	0.4

Table 21: Comparing instructional manipulation check failure to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.104					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.632	367	0.528	-0.012	-0.05	0.02
	SP	2.811	307	0.005	0.081	0.02	0.14
Scrolling	PC	1.572	376	0.117	0.036	-0.01	0.08
	SP	0.67	329	0.504	0.017	-0.03	0.06
Unfolding	PC	-0.924	381	0.356	-0.017	-0.05	0.02
	SP	-0.614	304	0.54	-0.012	-0.05	0.03
Horizontal scrolling	PC	0.801	370	0.424	0.017	-0.02	0.06
	SP	2.422	320	0.016	0.068	0.01	0.12
Paging	PC	-1.249	377	0.213	-0.022	-0.06	0.01
	SP	0.552	289	0.581	0.012	-0.03	0.06

Table 22: Comparing instructional manipulation check failure to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.138					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-2.466	367	0.014	-0.046	-0.08	-0.01
	SP	1.632	307	0.104	0.047	-0.01	0.1
Scrolling	PC	0.088	376	0.93	0.002	-0.04	0.05
	SP	-0.71	329	0.478	-0.017	-0.07	0.03
Unfolding	PC	-2.731	381	0.007	-0.051	-0.09	-0.01
	SP	-2.29	304	0.023	-0.046	-0.09	-0.01
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.81	370	0.419	-0.017	-0.06	0.02
	SP	1.214	320	0.226	0.034	-0.02	0.09
Paging	PC	-3.164	377	0.002	-0.056	-0.09	-0.02
	SP	-0.964	289	0.336	-0.022	-0.07	0.02

Table 23: Comparing outliers to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.0580					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	2.311	355	0.021	0.03576	0.0053	0.0662
	SP	1.085	267	0.279	0.01756	-0.0143	0.0494
Scrolling	PC	1.081	350	0.281	0.01503	-0.0123	0.0424
	SP	0.453	296	0.651	0.00647	-0.0216	0.0346
Unfolding	PC	-0.794	369	0.428	-0.00893	-0.031	0.0132
	SP	-0.416	276	0.678	-0.00558	-0.032	0.0208
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-3.004	322	0.003	-0.02838	-0.047	-0.0098
	SP	-1.887	262	0.06	-0.02179	-0.0445	0.0009
Paging	PC	-1.344	349	0.18	-0.01465	-0.0361	0.0068
	SP	0.417	248	0.677	0.0065	-0.0242	0.0372

Table 24: Comparing outliers to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 0.0598					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	2.195	355	0.029	0.03396	0.0035	0.0644
	SP	0.974	267	0.331	0.01576	-0.0161	0.0476
Scrolling	PC	0.951	350	0.342	0.01323	-0.0141	0.0406
	SP	0.327	296	0.744	0.00467	-0.0234	0.0328
Unfolding	PC	-0.954	369	0.341	-0.01073	-0.0328	0.0114
	SP	-0.55	276	0.583	-0.00738	-0.0338	0.019
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-3.195	322	0.002	-0.03018	-0.0488	-0.0116
	SP	-2.043	262	0.042	-0.02359	-0.0463	-0.0009
Paging	PC	-1.51	349	0.132	-0.01645	-0.0379	0.005
	SP	0.301	248	0.764	0.0047	-0.026	0.0354

1.2 Differences in RQIs between PCs and SPs across five layouts

Table 25: Comparing breakoffs between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	39.094	0	-3.095	917	0.002	-0.069	0.022	-0.113	-0.025
	Equal variances not assumed			-3.049	816.042	0.002	-0.069	0.023	-0.114	-0.025
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	34.36	0	-2.912	948	0.004	-0.067	0.023	-0.113	-0.022
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.874	855.964	0.004	-0.067	0.023	-0.113	-0.021
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	42.78	0	-3.248	916	0.001	-0.073	0.023	-0.117	-0.029
	Equal variances not assumed			-3.168	767.113	0.002	-0.073	0.023	-0.119	-0.028
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	82.797	0	-4.452	936	0	-0.102	0.023	-0.147	-0.057
	Equal variances not assumed			-4.359	791.606	0	-0.102	0.023	-0.148	-0.056
Paging	Equal variances assumed	104.708	0	-5.02	909	0	-0.125	0.025	-0.174	-0.076
	Equal variances not assumed			-4.892	751.49	0	-0.125	0.026	-0.175	-0.075

Table 26: Comparing item nonresponse between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.55	0.459	-0.499	881	0.618	0.00068	0.00137	-0.00336	0.002
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.494	810.414	0.622	0.00068	0.00138	-0.00339	0.00203
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	1.175	0.279	0.765	904	0.444	0.00114	0.00148	-0.00178	0.00405
	Equal variances not assumed			0.753	802.982	0.451	0.00114	0.00151	-0.00182	0.00409
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	7.368	0.007	1.415	879	0.157	0.00284	0.00201	-0.0011	0.00679
	Equal variances not assumed			1.558	591.069	0.12	0.00284	0.00182	-0.00074	0.00643
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	4.738	0.03	-2.936	895	0.003	0.00779	0.00265	-0.01299	-0.00258
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.923	853.49	0.004	0.00779	0.00266	-0.01302	-0.00256
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.621	0.431	0.487	860	0.626	0.00073	0.0015	-0.00222	0.00368
	Equal variances not assumed			0.507	812.912	0.612	0.00073	0.00144	-0.0021	0.00356

Table 27: Comparing straightlining between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.97	0.325	-0.605	818	0.545	-0.0324	0.05353	-0.13748	0.07267
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.601	764.272	0.548	-0.0324	0.05394	-0.13828	0.07348
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	1.918	0.166	0.75	832	0.454	0.03197	0.04265	-0.05175	0.11569
	Equal variances not assumed			0.756	821.463	0.45	0.03197	0.04227	-0.05099	0.11493
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	2.901	0.089	0.933	824	0.351	0.04067	0.0436	-0.0449	0.12624
	Equal variances not assumed			0.948	809.944	0.344	0.04067	0.04292	-0.04358	0.12492
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.288	0.592	0.111	822	0.912	0.00516	0.04658	-0.08628	0.0966
	Equal variances not assumed			0.112	803.545	0.911	0.00516	0.04612	-0.08537	0.09568
Paging	Equal variances assumed	3.387	0.066	-0.936	789	0.349	-0.03432	0.03665	-0.10625	0.03762
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.925	684.793	0.355	-0.03432	0.03709	-0.10713	0.0385

Table 28: Comparing extreme positive responses between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	10.173	0.001	-2.07	818	0.039	0.01776	0.00858	-0.03459	0.00092
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.009	651.312	0.045	0.01776	0.00884	-0.03512	0.0004
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	1.203	0.273	-1.857	832	0.064	0.01262	0.0068	-0.02596	0.00072
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.834	753.884	0.067	0.01262	0.00688	-0.02613	0.00089
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	1.369	0.242	-1.603	824	0.109	0.01117	0.00697	-0.02485	0.00251
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.579	724.215	0.115	0.01117	0.00707	-0.02506	0.00272
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	1.447	0.229	-1.487	825	0.138	0.00956	0.00643	-0.02219	0.00306
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.496	797.005	0.135	0.00956	0.00639	-0.02211	0.00299
Paging	Equal variances assumed	18.682	0	-2.786	792	0.005	0.02091	0.00751	-0.03564	0.00618
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.592	509.92	0.01	0.02091	0.00807	-0.03676	0.00506

Table 29: Comparing extreme negative responses between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	2.503	0.114	-0.973	818	0.331	0.00907	0.00932	-0.02735	0.00922
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.967	769.373	0.334	0.00907	0.00937	-0.02747	0.00934
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.838	0.36	-0.046	832	0.963	0.00036	0.00782	-0.01571	0.015
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.046	813.905	0.963	0.00036	0.00778	-0.01563	0.01491
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.055	0.815	0.144	824	0.885	0.00121	0.00838	-0.01524	0.01766
	Equal variances not assumed			0.144	754.035	0.886	0.00121	0.00843	-0.01535	0.01777
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	6.322	0.012	0.829	825	0.407	0.00613	0.0074	-0.00839	0.02065
	Equal variances not assumed			0.846	820.866	0.398	0.00613	0.00725	-0.0081	0.02037
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.767	0.382	-0.706	792	0.481	0.00628	0.0089	-0.02376	0.0112
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.704	716.35	0.482	0.00628	0.00893	-0.02381	0.01124

Table 30: Comparing midpoint responses between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.114	0.736	1.117	818	0.264	0.01461	0.01308	-0.01107	0.04029
	Equal variances not assumed			1.115	785.598	0.265	0.01461	0.01311	-0.01112	0.04034
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	3.985	0.046	1.08	832	0.28	0.0138	0.01277	-0.01127	0.03886
	Equal variances not assumed			1.093	825.825	0.275	0.0138	0.01262	-0.01097	0.03857
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	7.298	0.007	2.059	824	0.04	0.02534	0.01231	0.00118	0.04951
	Equal variances not assumed			2.107	819.662	0.035	0.02534	0.01203	0.00173	0.04896
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	1.298	0.255	-1.75	825	0.08	0.02145	0.01226	-0.04551	0.00261
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.745	771.418	0.081	0.02145	0.01229	-0.04559	0.00268
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.001	0.981	1.393	792	0.164	0.01724	0.01238	-0.00705	0.04153
	Equal variances not assumed			1.389	714.938	0.165	0.01724	0.01241	-0.00713	0.04161

Table 31: Comparing concurrent multitasking between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	12.421	0	1.783	794	0.075	0.055	0.031	-0.006	0.116
	Equal variances not assumed			1.814	791.324	0.07	0.055	0.03	-0.005	0.115
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	1.537	0.215	-0.558	806	0.577	-0.018	0.032	-0.08	0.045
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.553	736.572	0.58	-0.018	0.032	-0.081	0.045
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.053	0.818	-0.062	793	0.95	-0.002	0.035	-0.07	0.066
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.062	729.352	0.95	-0.002	0.035	-0.07	0.066
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	12.207	0.001	-1.686	801	0.092	-0.06	0.035	-0.129	0.01
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.631	635.47	0.103	-0.06	0.037	-0.132	0.012
Paging	Equal variances assumed	9.557	0.002	1.639	750	0.102	0.06	0.037	-0.012	0.132
	Equal variances not assumed			1.674	717.226	0.095	0.06	0.036	-0.01	0.131

Table 32: Comparing sequential multitasking between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Sequential MT, number	1.733	0.188	-0.878	794	0.38	-0.033	0.037	-0.106	0.04
				-0.89	788.124	0.374	-0.033	0.037	-0.105	0.039
Scrolling	Sequential MT, number	0.034	0.855	-0.255	806	0.799	-0.008	0.032	-0.07	0.054
				-0.259	800.348	0.796	-0.008	0.031	-0.069	0.053
Unfolding	Sequential MT, number	7.146	0.008	1.345	793	0.179	0.051	0.038	-0.024	0.126
				1.378	775.09	0.169	0.051	0.037	-0.022	0.124
Horizontal scrolling	Sequential MT, number	1.096	0.295	-0.634	801	0.526	-0.026	0.041	-0.106	0.054
				-0.635	750.785	0.526	-0.026	0.041	-0.106	0.054
Paging	Sequential MT, number	3.167	0.076	0.91	750	0.363	0.041	0.045	-0.048	0.13
				0.929	716.232	0.353	0.041	0.044	-0.046	0.128

Table 33: Comparing grid duration between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	6.419	0.011	1	795	0.317	19.19569	19.18826	-18.46997	56.86135
	Equal variances not assumed			0.982	693.728	0.326	19.19569	19.54054	-19.17	57.56138
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	19.773	0	3.816	806	0	77.28601	20.2557	37.52589	117.04613
	Equal variances not assumed			3.901	805.791	0	77.28601	19.81173	38.39732	116.1747
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.118	0.731	1.104	793	0.27	22.53297	20.41012	-17.5313	62.59725
	Equal variances not assumed			1.106	728.285	0.269	22.53297	20.37499	-17.46775	62.5337
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.648	0.421	-0.785	800	0.432	18.08379	23.02632	-63.28292	27.11533
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.781	730.953	0.435	18.08379	23.1523	-63.53673	27.36915
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.495	0.482	1.632	751	0.103	87.77265	53.7726	-17.78979	193.33509
	Equal variances not assumed			1.708	748.501	0.088	87.77265	51.39301	-13.11894	188.66425

Table 34: Comparing self-reported burden between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.317	0.574	0.922	796	0.357	0.055	0.06	-0.063	0.174
	Equal variances not assumed			0.921	758.427	0.358	0.055	0.06	-0.063	0.174
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.706	0.401	-0.523	807	0.601	-0.032	0.061	-0.152	0.088
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.521	751.951	0.603	-0.032	0.062	-0.153	0.089
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	3.857	0.05	-2.902	794	0.004	-0.192	0.066	-0.323	0.062
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.85	674.67	0.005	-0.192	0.068	-0.325	-0.06
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.023	0.88	-0.008	800	0.994	-0.001	0.065	-0.127	0.126
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.008	752.522	0.994	-0.001	0.064	-0.127	0.126
Paging	Equal variances assumed	1.062	0.303	-0.969	755	0.333	-0.071	0.073	-0.215	0.073
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.974	687.671	0.331	-0.071	0.073	-0.214	0.072

Table 35: Comparing instructional manipulation check failure between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	30.624	0	-2.789	675	0.005	-0.093	0.033	-0.158	0.027
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.706	537.326	0.007	-0.093	0.034	-0.16	0.025
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.989	0.32	0.58	705	0.562	0.02	0.034	-0.047	0.086
	Equal variances not assumed			0.58	691.386	0.562	0.02	0.034	-0.047	0.086
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.083	0.773	-0.178	685	0.859	-0.005	0.028	-0.06	0.05
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.179	661.237	0.858	-0.005	0.028	-0.059	0.049
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	8.931	0.003	-1.479	689	0.139	-0.051	0.035	-0.119	0.017
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.457	612.832	0.146	-0.051	0.035	-0.12	0.018
Paging	Equal variances assumed	5.397	0.02	-1.224	666	0.221	-0.035	0.028	-0.09	0.021
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.208	587.06	0.227	-0.035	0.029	-0.091	0.022

Table 36: Comparing outliers between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	2.596	0.108	0.802	621	0.423	0.0182	0.0227	-0.02638	0.06279
	Equal variances not assumed			0.813	600.141	0.417	0.0182	0.02239	-0.02578	0.06218
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.733	0.392	0.428	646	0.669	0.00856	0.02002	-0.03075	0.04787
	Equal variances not assumed			0.43	638.664	0.668	0.00856	0.01992	-0.03056	0.04768
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.148	0.701	-0.192	645	0.848	0.00335	0.01743	-0.03757	0.03087
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.191	584.05	0.848	0.00335	0.01751	-0.03774	0.03104
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.797	0.372	-0.446	584	0.655	0.00659	0.01477	-0.0356	0.02241
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.442	535.183	0.659	0.00659	0.01492	-0.03589	0.02271
Paging	Equal variances assumed	5.263	0.022	-1.147	597	0.252	0.02115	0.01844	-0.05736	0.01507
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.111	469.405	0.267	0.02115	0.01903	-0.05854	0.01625

2 T-tests for estimates

2.1 Differences in estimates between a specific layout and the five-layout average

Table 37: Comparing “Extraversion” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.96					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.191	439	0.849	-0.00727	-0.0822	0.0677
	SP	2.435	352	0.015	0.09269	0.0178	0.1676
Scrolling	PC	-0.15	447	0.881	-0.00514	-0.0726	0.0623
	SP	2.428	361	0.016	0.09885	0.0188	0.1789
Unfolding	PC	1.275	455	0.203	0.04273	-0.0231	0.1086
	SP	0.079	342	0.937	0.00314	-0.075	0.0813
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-1.019	451	0.309	-0.03487	-0.1022	0.0324
	SP	2.667	333	0.008	0.11049	0.029	0.192
Paging	PC	0.84	442	0.401	0.02945	-0.0394	0.0983
	SP	2.473	319	0.014	0.10308	0.0211	0.1851

Table 38: Comparing “Extraversion” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.04					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-2.288	439	0.023	-0.08727	-0.1622	-0.0123
	SP	0.333	352	0.739	0.01269	-0.0622	0.0876
Scrolling	PC	-2.48	447	0.014	-0.08514	-0.1526	-0.0177
	SP	0.463	361	0.644	0.01885	-0.0612	0.0989
Unfolding	PC	-1.112	455	0.267	-0.03727	-0.1031	0.0286
	SP	-1.934	342	0.054	-0.07686	-0.155	0.0013
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-3.355	451	0.001	-0.11487	-0.1822	-0.0476
	SP	0.736	333	0.462	0.03049	-0.051	0.112
Paging	PC	-1.442	442	0.15	-0.05055	-0.1194	0.0183
	SP	0.554	319	0.58	0.02308	-0.0589	0.1051

Table 39: Comparing “Agreeableness” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.48					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	1.472	438	0.142	0.04136	-0.0139	0.0966
	SP	2.925	351	0.004	0.09768	0.032	0.1634
Scrolling	PC	0.514	447	0.608	0.01368	-0.0386	0.066
	SP	-0.05	361	0.96	-0.0017	-0.0682	0.0648
Unfolding	PC	-1.142	456	0.254	-0.03187	-0.0867	0.0229
	SP	0.257	342	0.797	0.00852	-0.0566	0.0736
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.637	452	0.525	-0.01795	-0.0734	0.0375
	SP	-0.315	341	0.753	-0.01026	-0.0743	0.0538
Paging	PC	-0.837	442	0.403	-0.02325	-0.0779	0.0314
	SP	1.219	319	0.224	0.04581	-0.0281	0.1197

Table 40: Comparing “Agreeableness” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.51					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	0.404	438	0.686	0.01136	-0.0439	0.0666
	SP	2.027	351	0.043	0.06768	0.002	0.1334
Scrolling	PC	-0.613	447	0.54	-0.01632	-0.0686	0.036
	SP	-0.937	361	0.349	-0.0317	-0.0982	0.0348
Unfolding	PC	-2.218	456	0.027	-0.06187	-0.1167	-0.0071
	SP	-0.649	342	0.517	-0.02148	-0.0866	0.0436
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-1.7	452	0.09	-0.04795	-0.1034	0.0075
	SP	-1.236	341	0.217	-0.04026	-0.1043	0.0238
Paging	PC	-1.916	442	0.056	-0.05325	-0.1079	0.0014
	SP	0.421	319	0.674	0.01581	-0.0581	0.0897

Table 41: Comparing “Conscientiousness” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.79					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	0.334	440	0.739	0.0105	-0.0513	0.0723
	SP	-1.651	350	0.1	-0.05365	-0.1176	0.0103
Scrolling	PC	0.319	446	0.75	0.00873	-0.0451	0.0625
	SP	-3.292	362	0.001	-0.11446	-0.1828	-0.0461
Unfolding	PC	-1.717	456	0.087	-0.04851	-0.104	0.007
	SP	-3.061	345	0.002	-0.10606	-0.1742	-0.0379
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-1.401	447	0.162	-0.03905	-0.0939	0.0157
	SP	-4.591	333	0	-0.16312	-0.233	-0.0932
Paging	PC	2.41	439	0.016	0.06407	0.0118	0.1163
	SP	-0.537	316	0.591	-0.01942	-0.0906	0.0517

Table 42: Comparing “Conscientiousness” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.70					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	3.195	440	0.001	0.1005	0.0387	0.1623
	SP	1.118	350	0.264	0.03635	-0.0276	0.1003
Scrolling	PC	3.608	446	0	0.09873	0.0449	0.1525
	SP	-0.704	362	0.482	-0.02446	-0.0928	0.0439
Unfolding	PC	1.468	456	0.143	0.04149	-0.014	0.097
	SP	-0.463	345	0.643	-0.01606	-0.0842	0.0521
Horizontal scrolling	PC	1.827	447	0.068	0.05095	-0.0039	0.1057
	SP	-2.058	333	0.04	-0.07312	-0.143	-0.0032
Paging	PC	5.796	439	0	0.15407	0.1018	0.2063
	SP	1.952	316	0.052	0.07058	-0.0006	0.1417

Table 43: Comparing “Neuroticism” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.82					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.432	436	0.153	-0.04939	-0.1172	0.0184
	SP	2.24	351	0.026	0.07357	0.009	0.1382
Scrolling	PC	0.477	448	0.634	0.01478	-0.0462	0.0757
	SP	3.148	361	0.002	0.11276	0.0423	0.1832
Unfolding	PC	-0.064	455	0.949	-0.00192	-0.061	0.0571
	SP	2.464	343	0.014	0.09366	0.0189	0.1684
Horizontal scrolling	PC	1.703	450	0.089	0.05282	-0.0081	0.1138
	SP	3.154	338	0.002	0.10754	0.0405	0.1746
Paging	PC	-0.863	440	0.389	-0.02805	-0.0919	0.0358
	SP	1.098	319	0.273	0.04403	-0.0349	0.1229

Table 44: Comparing “Neuroticism” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.90					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-3.752	436	0	-0.12939	-0.1972	-0.0616
	SP	-0.196	351	0.845	-0.00643	-0.071	0.0582
Scrolling	PC	-2.103	448	0.036	-0.06522	-0.1262	-0.0043
	SP	0.914	361	0.361	0.03276	-0.0377	0.1032
Unfolding	PC	-2.726	455	0.007	-0.08192	-0.141	-0.0229
	SP	0.359	343	0.72	0.01366	-0.0611	0.0884
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.876	450	0.381	-0.02718	-0.0881	0.0338
	SP	0.808	338	0.42	0.02754	-0.0395	0.0946
Paging	PC	-3.324	440	0.001	-0.10805	-0.1719	-0.0442
	SP	-0.897	319	0.37	-0.03597	-0.1149	0.0429

Table 45: Comparing “Imagination” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.24					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	0.23	437	0.818	0.00764	-0.0576	0.0729
	SP	1.816	349	0.07	0.06438	-0.0054	0.1341
Scrolling	PC	-0.41	447	0.682	-0.01257	-0.0728	0.0477
	SP	2.72	361	0.007	0.0849	0.0235	0.1463
Unfolding	PC	-0.01	456	0.992	-0.00032	-0.0629	0.0622
	SP	2.708	344	0.007	0.0922	0.0252	0.1592
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.227	452	0.821	-0.0075	-0.0725	0.0575
	SP	0.615	338	0.539	0.02376	-0.0522	0.0998
Paging	PC	-0.329	439	0.742	-0.01087	-0.0757	0.054
	SP	1.379	318	0.169	0.05329	-0.0227	0.1293

Table 46: Comparing “Imagination” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.30					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.578	437	0.115	-0.05236	-0.1176	0.0129
	SP	0.124	349	0.902	0.00438	-0.0654	0.0741
Scrolling	PC	-2.367	447	0.018	-0.07257	-0.1328	-0.0123
	SP	0.798	361	0.426	0.0249	-0.0365	0.0863
Unfolding	PC	-1.895	456	0.059	-0.06032	-0.1229	0.0022
	SP	0.946	344	0.345	0.0322	-0.0348	0.0992
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-2.04	452	0.042	-0.0675	-0.1325	-0.0025
	SP	-0.938	338	0.349	-0.03624	-0.1122	0.0398
Paging	PC	-2.147	439	0.032	-0.07087	-0.1357	-0.006
	SP	-0.174	318	0.862	-0.00671	-0.0827	0.0693

Table 47: Comparing “Auto completion of text” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.69					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.934	443	0.351	-0.046	-0.14	0.05
	SP	0.167	359	0.868	0.01	-0.11	0.13
Scrolling	PC	0.962	451	0.337	0.046	-0.05	0.14
	SP	2.063	367	0.04	0.109	0.01	0.21
Unfolding	PC	0.445	456	0.657	0.02	-0.07	0.11
	SP	1.265	350	0.207	0.074	-0.04	0.19
Horizontal scrolling	PC	0.417	457	0.677	0.019	-0.07	0.11
	SP	0.074	357	0.941	0.004	-0.1	0.11
Paging	PC	-0.618	445	0.537	-0.03	-0.12	0.06
	SP	-1.547	326	0.123	-0.086	-0.2	0.02

Table 48: Comparing “Auto completion of text” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.71					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.342	443	0.18	-0.066	-0.16	0.03
	SP	-0.172	359	0.864	-0.01	-0.13	0.11
Scrolling	PC	0.547	451	0.585	0.026	-0.07	0.12
	SP	1.683	367	0.093	0.089	-0.01	0.19
Unfolding	PC	0.007	456	0.994	0	-0.09	0.09
	SP	0.921	350	0.358	0.054	-0.06	0.17
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.017	457	0.986	-0.001	-0.09	0.09
	SP	-0.301	357	0.763	-0.016	-0.12	0.09
Paging	PC	-1.034	445	0.302	-0.05	-0.14	0.04
	SP	-1.905	326	0.058	-0.106	-0.22	0

Table 49: Comparing “Spelling and grammar check” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.33					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	0.041	444	0.967	0.002	-0.09	0.09
	SP	-0.31	359	0.757	-0.017	-0.12	0.09
Scrolling	PC	0.614	449	0.54	0.029	-0.06	0.12
	SP	0.04	367	0.968	0.002	-0.1	0.1
Unfolding	PC	-0.496	455	0.62	-0.023	-0.11	0.07
	SP	-1.722	348	0.086	-0.1	-0.21	0.01
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.555	446	0.579	-0.026	-0.12	0.07
	SP	-0.348	355	0.728	-0.017	-0.11	0.08
Paging	PC	0.862	444	0.389	0.04	-0.05	0.13
	SP	-4.379	325	0	-0.26	-0.38	-0.14

Table 50: Comparing “Spelling and grammar check” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.25					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	1.764	444	0.078	0.082	-0.01	0.17
	SP	1.168	359	0.244	0.063	-0.04	0.17
Scrolling	PC	2.32	449	0.021	0.109	0.02	0.2
	SP	1.607	367	0.109	0.082	-0.02	0.18
Unfolding	PC	1.264	455	0.207	0.057	-0.03	0.15
	SP	-0.348	348	0.728	-0.02	-0.13	0.09
Horizontal scrolling	PC	1.14	446	0.255	0.054	-0.04	0.15
	SP	1.28	355	0.201	0.063	-0.03	0.16
Paging	PC	2.583	444	0.01	0.12	0.03	0.21
	SP	-3.034	325	0.003	-0.18	-0.3	-0.06

Table 51: Comparing “Selecting a playlist to match my musical preferences” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.89					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.648	442	0.517	-0.03	-0.12	0.06
	SP	2.957	360	0.003	0.154	0.05	0.26
Scrolling	PC	0.672	449	0.502	0.033	-0.06	0.13
	SP	3.477	367	0.001	0.181	0.08	0.28
Unfolding	PC	0.538	456	0.591	0.025	-0.07	0.11
	SP	1.471	350	0.142	0.08	-0.03	0.19
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.552	447	0.582	-0.025	-0.11	0.06
	SP	2.27	357	0.024	0.119	0.02	0.22
Paging	PC	-0.105	443	0.917	-0.005	-0.09	0.08
	SP	2.776	326	0.006	0.164	0.05	0.28

Table 52: Comparing “Selecting a playlist to match my musical preferences” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.03					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-3.665	442	0	-0.17	-0.26	-0.08
	SP	0.271	360	0.787	0.014	-0.09	0.12
Scrolling	PC	-2.209	449	0.028	-0.107	-0.2	-0.01
	SP	0.793	367	0.428	0.041	-0.06	0.14
Unfolding	PC	-2.522	456	0.012	-0.115	-0.21	-0.03
	SP	-1.094	350	0.275	-0.06	-0.17	0.05
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-3.626	447	0	-0.165	-0.25	-0.08
	SP	-0.403	357	0.687	-0.021	-0.12	0.08
Paging	PC	-3.195	443	0.001	-0.145	-0.23	-0.06
	SP	0.403	326	0.687	0.024	-0.09	0.14

Table 53: Comparing “Selecting the best and most efficient route in my GPS navigation app while driving” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.44					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.31	443	0.191	-0.063	-0.16	0.03
	SP	0.626	359	0.532	0.032	-0.07	0.13
Scrolling	PC	1.6	451	0.11	0.069	-0.02	0.15
	SP	3.034	366	0.003	0.147	0.05	0.24
Unfolding	PC	-0.854	456	0.394	-0.037	-0.12	0.05
	SP	2.045	347	0.042	0.101	0	0.2
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-1.134	449	0.258	-0.051	-0.14	0.04
	SP	2.621	356	0.009	0.121	0.03	0.21
Paging	PC	1.824	443	0.069	0.075	-0.01	0.16
	SP	4.269	326	0	0.207	0.11	0.3

Table 54: Comparing “Selecting the best and most efficient route in my GPS navigation app while driving” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.56					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-3.817	443	0	-0.183	-0.28	-0.09
	SP	-1.717	359	0.087	-0.088	-0.19	0.01
Scrolling	PC	-1.168	451	0.243	-0.051	-0.14	0.03
	SP	0.564	366	0.573	0.027	-0.07	0.12
Unfolding	PC	-3.593	456	0	-0.157	-0.24	-0.07
	SP	-0.385	347	0.701	-0.019	-0.12	0.08
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-3.816	449	0	-0.171	-0.26	-0.08
	SP	0.02	356	0.984	0.001	-0.09	0.09
Paging	PC	-1.091	443	0.276	-0.045	-0.13	0.04
	SP	1.791	326	0.074	0.087	-0.01	0.18

Table 55: Comparing “Autonomous driving of a motor vehicle” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.48					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.466	444	0.143	-0.073	-0.17	0.03
	SP	-2.616	359	0.009	-0.149	-0.26	-0.04
Scrolling	PC	1.08	449	0.281	0.052	-0.04	0.15
	SP	2.22	365	0.027	0.129	0.01	0.24
Unfolding	PC	2.64	457	0.009	0.13	0.03	0.23
	SP	2.059	349	0.04	0.122	0.01	0.24
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.648	449	0.517	-0.03	-0.12	0.06
	SP	2.861	354	0.004	0.164	0.05	0.28
Paging	PC	-1.446	442	0.149	-0.07	-0.17	0.03
	SP	-1.053	325	0.293	-0.063	-0.18	0.05

Table 56: Comparing “Autonomous driving of a motor vehicle” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.52					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-2.265	444	0.024	-0.113	-0.21	-0.01
	SP	-3.317	359	0.001	-0.189	-0.3	-0.08
Scrolling	PC	0.253	449	0.8	0.012	-0.08	0.11
	SP	1.532	365	0.126	0.089	-0.03	0.2
Unfolding	PC	1.829	457	0.068	0.09	-0.01	0.19
	SP	1.384	349	0.167	0.082	-0.03	0.2
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-1.498	449	0.135	-0.07	-0.16	0.02
	SP	2.163	354	0.031	0.124	0.01	0.24
Paging	PC	-2.266	442	0.024	-0.11	-0.21	-0.01
	SP	-1.722	325	0.086	-0.103	-0.22	0.01

Table 57: Comparing “Diagnosis of my medical status by an AI system” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.25					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.768	443	0.078	-0.082	-0.17	0.01
	SP	-0.789	359	0.431	-0.045	-0.16	0.07
Scrolling	PC	0.215	451	0.83	0.01	-0.08	0.1
	SP	1.284	367	0.2	0.069	-0.04	0.17
Unfolding	PC	1.163	456	0.245	0.056	-0.04	0.15
	SP	2.252	349	0.025	0.126	0.02	0.24
Horizontal scrolling	PC	0.997	443	0.319	0.045	-0.04	0.13
	SP	2.245	354	0.025	0.124	0.02	0.23
Paging	PC	-1.381	442	0.168	-0.062	-0.15	0.03
	SP	0.399	326	0.69	0.022	-0.09	0.13

Table 58: Comparing “Diagnosis of my medical status by an AI system” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.31					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-3.063	443	0.002	-0.142	-0.23	-0.05
	SP	-1.833	359	0.068	-0.105	-0.22	0.01
Scrolling	PC	-1.085	451	0.279	-0.05	-0.14	0.04
	SP	0.163	367	0.871	0.009	-0.1	0.11
Unfolding	PC	-0.093	456	0.926	-0.004	-0.1	0.09
	SP	1.18	349	0.239	0.066	-0.04	0.18
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.327	443	0.744	-0.015	-0.1	0.07
	SP	1.157	354	0.248	0.064	-0.04	0.17
Paging	PC	-2.709	442	0.007	-0.122	-0.21	-0.03
	SP	-0.682	326	0.496	-0.038	-0.15	0.07

Table 59: Comparing “The variety and ease of online shopping sometimes leads me to make purchases that I later find unnecessary” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.65					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.379	370	0.705	-0.023	-0.14	0.1
	SP	2.381	304	0.018	0.176	0.03	0.32
Scrolling	PC	1.013	373	0.312	0.061	-0.06	0.18
	SP	2.743	309	0.006	0.185	0.05	0.32
Unfolding	PC	0.554	380	0.58	0.032	-0.08	0.14
	SP	2.06	294	0.04	0.135	0.01	0.26
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.458	360	0.647	-0.027	-0.14	0.09
	SP	5.154	301	0	0.332	0.21	0.46
Paging	PC	-0.332	370	0.74	-0.02	-0.14	0.1
	SP	2.449	268	0.015	0.171	0.03	0.31

Table 60: Comparing “The variety and ease of online shopping sometimes leads me to make purchases that I later find unnecessary” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.85					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-3.7	370	0	-0.223	-0.34	-0.1
	SP	-0.332	304	0.74	-0.024	-0.17	0.12
Scrolling	PC	-2.303	373	0.022	-0.139	-0.26	-0.02
	SP	-0.225	309	0.822	-0.015	-0.15	0.12
Unfolding	PC	-2.958	380	0.003	-0.168	-0.28	-0.06
	SP	-0.991	294	0.322	-0.065	-0.19	0.06
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-3.828	360	0	-0.227	-0.34	-0.11
	SP	2.052	301	0.041	0.132	0.01	0.26
Paging	PC	-3.676	370	0	-0.22	-0.34	-0.1
	SP	-0.409	268	0.683	-0.029	-0.17	0.11

Table 61: Comparing “User ratings and reviews of products and services can be trusted” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.05					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.559	369	0.577	-0.022	-0.1	0.06
	SP	1.184	304	0.237	0.063	-0.04	0.17
Scrolling	PC	0.63	373	0.529	0.025	-0.05	0.1
	SP	1.672	308	0.096	0.083	-0.01	0.18
Unfolding	PC	-0.135	378	0.893	-0.005	-0.08	0.07
	SP	-0.143	294	0.886	-0.007	-0.1	0.09
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.724	360	0.469	-0.031	-0.12	0.05
	SP	2.984	301	0.003	0.126	0.04	0.21
Paging	PC	0.5	370	0.617	0.021	-0.06	0.1
	SP	3.13	265	0.002	0.158	0.06	0.26

Table 62: Comparing “User ratings and reviews of products and services can be trusted” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.13					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-2.553	369	0.011	-0.102	-0.18	-0.02
	SP	-0.329	304	0.742	-0.017	-0.12	0.09
Scrolling	PC	-1.371	373	0.171	-0.055	-0.13	0.02
	SP	0.061	308	0.951	0.003	-0.09	0.1
Unfolding	PC	-2.186	378	0.029	-0.085	-0.16	-0.01
	SP	-1.847	294	0.066	-0.087	-0.18	0.01
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-2.577	360	0.01	-0.111	-0.2	-0.03
	SP	1.095	301	0.274	0.046	-0.04	0.13
Paging	PC	-1.445	370	0.149	-0.059	-0.14	0.02
	SP	1.547	265	0.123	0.078	-0.02	0.18

Table 63: Comparing “I prefer to tangibly test, see and "feel" the product that I buy” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.50					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	1.148	445	0.252	0.055	-0.04	0.15
	SP	-0.956	369	0.34	-0.05	-0.15	0.05
Scrolling	PC	0.607	455	0.544	0.025	-0.06	0.11
	SP	-2.43	370	0.016	-0.127	-0.23	-0.02
Unfolding	PC	-0.155	461	0.877	-0.007	-0.1	0.08
	SP	-1.969	358	0.05	-0.1	-0.2	0
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.1	458	0.921	-0.004	-0.08	0.08
	SP	-4.084	363	0	-0.204	-0.3	-0.11
Paging	PC	-1.751	453	0.081	-0.079	-0.17	0.01
	SP	-0.218	332	0.828	-0.012	-0.12	0.09

Table 64: Comparing “I prefer to tangibly test, see and "feel" the product that I buy” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.40					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	3.251	445	0.001	0.155	0.06	0.25
	SP	0.942	369	0.347	0.05	-0.05	0.15
Scrolling	PC	3.039	455	0.003	0.125	0.04	0.21
	SP	-0.522	370	0.602	-0.027	-0.13	0.08
Unfolding	PC	2.015	461	0.044	0.093	0	0.18
	SP	0.01	358	0.992	0	-0.1	0.1
Horizontal scrolling	PC	2.364	458	0.019	0.096	0.02	0.18
	SP	-2.079	363	0.038	-0.104	-0.2	-0.01
Paging	PC	0.457	453	0.648	0.021	-0.07	0.11
	SP	1.625	332	0.105	0.088	-0.02	0.19

Table 65: Comparing “Long delivery times deter me from making an on-line purchase” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.17					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.398	445	0.163	-0.072	-0.17	0.03
	SP	0.387	367	0.699	0.023	-0.09	0.14
Scrolling	PC	0.474	455	0.636	0.022	-0.07	0.11
	SP	1.108	370	0.269	0.059	-0.05	0.16
Unfolding	PC	-1.914	455	0.056	-0.095	-0.19	0
	SP	2.535	355	0.012	0.133	0.03	0.24
Horizontal scrolling	PC	0.961	449	0.337	0.045	-0.05	0.14
	SP	-0.398	360	0.691	-0.022	-0.13	0.09
Paging	PC	1.73	452	0.084	0.081	-0.01	0.17
	SP	2.443	332	0.015	0.138	0.03	0.25

Table 66: Comparing “Long delivery times deter me from making an on-line purchase” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.24					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-2.76	445	0.006	-0.142	-0.24	-0.04
	SP	-0.81	367	0.419	-0.047	-0.16	0.07
Scrolling	PC	-1.031	455	0.303	-0.048	-0.14	0.04
	SP	-0.197	370	0.844	-0.011	-0.12	0.09
Unfolding	PC	-3.329	455	0.001	-0.165	-0.26	-0.07
	SP	1.202	355	0.23	0.063	-0.04	0.17
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.548	449	0.584	-0.025	-0.12	0.07
	SP	-1.649	360	0.1	-0.092	-0.2	0.02
Paging	PC	0.241	452	0.809	0.011	-0.08	0.1
	SP	1.203	332	0.23	0.068	-0.04	0.18

Table 67: Comparing “I have trust concerns about receiving or returning goods” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.16					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	1.373	445	0.171	0.068	-0.03	0.17
	SP	0.687	365	0.493	0.038	-0.07	0.15
Scrolling	PC	-0.254	455	0.8	-0.012	-0.11	0.08
	SP	1.037	369	0.301	0.055	-0.05	0.16
Unfolding	PC	-1.494	461	0.136	-0.07	-0.16	0.02
	SP	0.212	356	0.832	0.012	-0.1	0.12
Horizontal scrolling	PC	0.779	447	0.436	0.037	-0.06	0.13
	SP	-0.322	357	0.748	-0.017	-0.12	0.09
Paging	PC	-0.509	450	0.611	-0.023	-0.11	0.07
	SP	-0.284	332	0.776	-0.016	-0.13	0.1

Table 68: Comparing “I have trust concerns about receiving or returning goods” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.17					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	1.171	445	0.242	0.058	-0.04	0.16
	SP	0.507	365	0.612	0.028	-0.08	0.14
Scrolling	PC	-0.463	455	0.644	-0.022	-0.12	0.07
	SP	0.848	369	0.397	0.045	-0.06	0.15
Unfolding	PC	-1.706	461	0.089	-0.08	-0.17	0.01
	SP	0.031	356	0.975	0.002	-0.11	0.11
Horizontal scrolling	PC	0.566	447	0.572	0.027	-0.07	0.12
	SP	-0.507	357	0.612	-0.027	-0.13	0.08
Paging	PC	-0.729	450	0.467	-0.033	-0.12	0.06
	SP	-0.458	332	0.647	-0.026	-0.14	0.09

Table 69: Comparing “I’m unable to buy online because I do not have a credit card” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 1.97					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	0.375	443	0.708	0.022	-0.09	0.14
	SP	2.391	364	0.017	0.171	0.03	0.31
Scrolling	PC	0.709	454	0.478	0.041	-0.07	0.16
	SP	1.82	370	0.069	0.119	-0.01	0.25
Unfolding	PC	0.087	458	0.93	0.005	-0.1	0.11
	SP	1.948	355	0.052	0.131	0	0.26
Horizontal scrolling	PC	1.491	448	0.137	0.085	-0.03	0.2
	SP	2.019	354	0.044	0.134	0	0.26
Paging	PC	-2.447	452	0.015	-0.127	-0.23	-0.03
	SP	0.158	332	0.874	0.011	-0.12	0.15

Table 70: Comparing “I’m unable to buy online because I do not have a credit card” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.08					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.511	443	0.131	-0.088	-0.2	0.03
	SP	0.856	364	0.392	0.061	-0.08	0.2
Scrolling	PC	-1.183	454	0.237	-0.069	-0.18	0.05
	SP	0.134	370	0.893	0.009	-0.12	0.14
Unfolding	PC	-1.926	458	0.055	-0.105	-0.21	0
	SP	0.314	355	0.753	0.021	-0.11	0.15
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.442	448	0.658	-0.025	-0.14	0.09
	SP	0.356	354	0.722	0.024	-0.11	0.15
Paging	PC	-4.565	452	0	-0.237	-0.34	-0.14
	SP	-1.444	332	0.15	-0.099	-0.23	0.04

Table 71: Comparing “I am concerned about website security while shopping online” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.23					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.311	444	0.191	-0.071	-0.18	0.04
	SP	-1.852	363	0.065	-0.111	-0.23	0.01
Scrolling	PC	0.127	454	0.899	0.006	-0.09	0.1
	SP	-0.702	370	0.483	-0.039	-0.15	0.07
Unfolding	PC	-0.23	461	0.818	-0.012	-0.11	0.09
	SP	-1.1	356	0.272	-0.061	-0.17	0.05
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.046	446	0.963	-0.002	-0.09	0.09
	SP	-1.489	356	0.137	-0.078	-0.18	0.03
Paging	PC	0.991	450	0.322	0.048	-0.05	0.14
	SP	-0.825	332	0.41	-0.048	-0.16	0.07

Table 72: Comparing “I am concerned about website security while shopping online” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.16					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.022	444	0.982	-0.001	-0.11	0.11
	SP	-0.682	363	0.496	-0.041	-0.16	0.08
Scrolling	PC	1.549	454	0.122	0.076	-0.02	0.17
	SP	0.563	370	0.574	0.031	-0.08	0.14
Unfolding	PC	1.157	461	0.248	0.058	-0.04	0.16
	SP	0.155	356	0.877	0.009	-0.1	0.12
Horizontal scrolling	PC	1.442	446	0.15	0.068	-0.02	0.16
	SP	-0.153	356	0.879	-0.008	-0.11	0.1
Paging	PC	2.439	450	0.015	0.118	0.02	0.21
	SP	0.371	332	0.711	0.022	-0.09	0.14

Table 73: Comparing “I am concerned about the privacy of personal data while shopping online” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.30					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-1.213	444	0.226	-0.063	-0.17	0.04
	SP	-0.614	366	0.54	-0.035	-0.15	0.08
Scrolling	PC	-0.627	453	0.531	-0.031	-0.13	0.07
	SP	-1.771	370	0.077	-0.102	-0.21	0.01
Unfolding	PC	-0.545	461	0.586	-0.026	-0.12	0.07
	SP	-0.39	358	0.697	-0.023	-0.14	0.09
Horizontal scrolling	PC	0.023	447	0.981	0.001	-0.09	0.1
	SP	-2.72	357	0.007	-0.15	-0.26	-0.04
Paging	PC	2.39	449	0.017	0.111	0.02	0.2
	SP	-0.231	332	0.817	-0.014	-0.13	0.11

Table 74: Comparing “I am concerned about the privacy of personal data while shopping online” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 3.24					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	-0.061	444	0.952	-0.003	-0.11	0.1
	SP	0.448	366	0.655	0.025	-0.09	0.14
Scrolling	PC	0.578	453	0.563	0.029	-0.07	0.13
	SP	-0.727	370	0.468	-0.042	-0.15	0.07
Unfolding	PC	0.702	461	0.483	0.034	-0.06	0.13
	SP	0.629	358	0.53	0.037	-0.08	0.15
Horizontal scrolling	PC	1.26	447	0.208	0.061	-0.03	0.16
	SP	-1.628	357	0.104	-0.09	-0.2	0.02
Paging	PC	3.688	449	0	0.171	0.08	0.26
	SP	0.756	332	0.45	0.046	-0.07	0.17

Table 75: Comparing “I lack the necessary digital skills to shop online” to five-layout average for PCs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.20					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	1.082	445	0.28	0.06	-0.05	0.17
	SP	-2.793	367	0.005	-0.168	-0.29	-0.05
Scrolling	PC	-1.656	454	0.098	-0.087	-0.19	0.02
	SP	-1.537	370	0.125	-0.092	-0.21	0.03
Unfolding	PC	0.118	461	0.906	0.007	-0.1	0.12
	SP	0.481	358	0.631	0.03	-0.09	0.15
Horizontal scrolling	PC	-0.002	445	0.998	0	-0.11	0.11
	SP	-0.742	356	0.458	-0.046	-0.17	0.08
Paging	PC	0.099	451	0.921	0.005	-0.1	0.11
	SP	-1.736	332	0.084	-0.11	-0.23	0.01

Table 76: Comparing “I lack the necessary digital skills to shop online” to five-layout average for SPs

One-Sample Test							
Experimental cell	Device	Test Value = 2.12					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Grid	PC	2.53	445	0.012	0.14	0.03	0.25
	SP	-1.466	367	0.144	-0.088	-0.21	0.03
Scrolling	PC	-0.139	454	0.889	-0.007	-0.11	0.1
	SP	-0.206	370	0.837	-0.012	-0.13	0.11
Unfolding	PC	1.566	461	0.118	0.087	-0.02	0.2
	SP	1.779	358	0.076	0.11	-0.01	0.23
Horizontal scrolling	PC	1.413	445	0.158	0.08	-0.03	0.19
	SP	0.542	356	0.588	0.034	-0.09	0.16
Paging	PC	1.588	451	0.113	0.085	-0.02	0.19
	SP	-0.474	332	0.636	-0.03	-0.15	0.09

2.2 Differences in estimates between PC and SPs across five layouts

Table 77: Comparing “Extraversion” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	2.303	0.13	-1.832	791	0.067	0.09996	0.05455	-0.20704	0.00713
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.855	781.248	0.064	0.09996	0.05389	-0.20574	0.00582
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.73	0.393	-1.966	808	0.05	0.10399	0.0529	-0.20782	0.00016
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.953	750.248	0.051	0.10399	0.05326	-0.20854	0.00056
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	1.106	0.293	0.765	797	0.445	0.03959	0.05178	-0.06206	0.14124
	Equal variances not assumed			0.761	725.477	0.447	0.03959	0.05199	-0.06248	0.14166
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.006	0.938	-2.721	783	0.007	0.14537	0.05343	-0.25025	0.04049
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.705	700.841	0.007	0.14537	0.05374	-0.25089	0.03985
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.013	0.909	-1.354	761	0.176	0.07363	0.05437	-0.18037	0.03311
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.352	683.031	0.177	0.07363	0.05446	-0.18056	0.03331

Table 78: Comparing “Agreeableness” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	3.487	0.062	-1.299	789	0.194	-0.05632	0.04334	-0.1414	0.02876
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.291	730.512	0.197	-0.05632	0.04364	-0.142	0.02935
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	5.47	0.02	0.362	808	0.717	0.01538	0.04243	-0.06792	0.09867
	Equal variances not assumed			0.357	722.498	0.721	0.01538	0.04303	-0.06911	0.09986
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.27	0.603	-0.937	798	0.349	0.04039	0.04311	-0.12501	0.04423
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.933	726.44	0.351	0.04039	0.04328	-0.12537	0.04459
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.013	0.908	-0.179	792	0.858	0.00769	0.04307	-0.09225	0.07686
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.179	732.209	0.858	0.00769	0.04309	-0.0923	0.07691
Paging	Equal variances assumed	5.465	0.02	-1.511	761	0.131	0.06906	0.04571	-0.15879	0.02067
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.478	627.624	0.14	0.06906	0.04674	-0.16085	0.02272

Table 79: Comparing “Conscientiousness” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.901	0.343	1.405	790	0.16	0.06415	0.04564	-0.02545	0.15375
	Equal variances not assumed			1.418	772.982	0.156	0.06415	0.04523	-0.02463	0.15293
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	6.446	0.011	2.823	808	0.005	0.12319	0.04363	0.03755	0.20884
	Equal variances not assumed			2.784	724.054	0.006	0.12319	0.04425	0.03633	0.21006
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	2.216	0.137	1.299	801	0.194	0.05755	0.04431	-0.02943	0.14453
	Equal variances not assumed			1.287	716.33	0.198	0.05755	0.04471	-0.03022	0.14532
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	4.416	0.036	2.786	780	0.005	0.12407	0.04454	0.03664	0.2115
	Equal variances not assumed			2.747	678.064	0.006	0.12407	0.04516	0.03539	0.21275
Paging	Equal variances assumed	5.156	0.023	1.904	755	0.057	0.08349	0.04385	-0.00258	0.16957
	Equal variances not assumed			1.861	619.691	0.063	0.08349	0.04488	-0.00464	0.17162

Table 80: Comparing “Neuroticism” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	9.428	0.002	-2.539	787	0.011	0.12296	0.04842	-0.21801	0.02791
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.582	784.355	0.01	0.12296	0.04763	-0.21646	0.02947
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.176	0.675	-2.076	808	0.038	0.09798	0.04719	-0.19062	0.00534
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.068	759.627	0.039	0.09798	0.04738	-0.19099	0.00497
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	4.767	0.029	-1.999	798	0.046	0.09558	0.04782	-0.18944	0.00171
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.973	699.798	0.049	0.09558	0.04845	-0.19071	0.00045
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.426	0.514	-1.179	787	0.239	0.05472	0.0464	-0.14581	0.03637
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.187	744.735	0.236	0.05472	0.04609	-0.14519	0.03576
Paging	Equal variances assumed	1.252	0.264	-1.408	759	0.16	0.07209	0.05121	-0.17262	0.02845
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.396	666.802	0.163	0.07209	0.05162	-0.17344	0.02927

Table 81: Comparing “Imagination” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.634	0.426	-1.162	786	0.245	0.05674	0.04881	-0.15256	0.03907
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.168	761.051	0.243	0.05674	0.04856	-0.15207	0.03859
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	1.106	0.293	-2.207	808	0.028	0.09747	0.04416	-0.18416	0.01078
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.228	795.61	0.026	0.09747	0.04375	-0.18335	0.01159
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.032	0.857	-1.965	800	0.05	0.09252	0.04709	-0.18495	0.0001
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.985	766.578	0.048	0.09252	0.04661	-0.18403	0.00102
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.735	0.392	-0.615	790	0.539	0.03125	0.0508	-0.13098	0.06847
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.614	723.905	0.539	0.03125	0.05087	-0.13112	0.06862
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.096	0.756	-1.262	757	0.207	0.06416	0.05084	-0.16396	0.03565
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.263	686.19	0.207	0.06416	0.05081	-0.16393	0.03561

Table 82: Comparing “Auto completion of text” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	2.992	0.084	-0.731	802	0.465	-0.056	0.076	-0.205	0.094
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.725	739.548	0.469	-0.056	0.077	-0.206	0.095
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.635	0.426	-0.871	818	0.384	-0.062	0.071	-0.202	0.078
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.872	789.09	0.383	-0.062	0.071	-0.202	0.078
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	6.926	0.009	-0.73	806	0.466	-0.053	0.073	-0.196	0.09
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.719	708.974	0.472	-0.053	0.074	-0.198	0.092
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.003	0.958	0.217	815	0.828	0.015	0.07	-0.123	0.153
	Equal variances not assumed			0.217	759.666	0.828	0.015	0.07	-0.123	0.153
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.007	0.933	0.769	770	0.442	0.057	0.074	-0.088	0.202
	Equal variances not assumed			0.769	703.702	0.442	0.057	0.074	-0.088	0.201

Table 83: Comparing “Spelling and grammar check” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	1.052	0.305	0.264	803	0.792	0.019	0.071	-0.121	0.158
	Equal variances not assumed			0.262	752.072	0.793	0.019	0.071	-0.121	0.159
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.002	0.961	0.385	816	0.7	0.027	0.069	-0.11	0.163
	Equal variances not assumed			0.386	788.597	0.7	0.027	0.069	-0.109	0.163
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	4.318	0.038	1.068	803	0.286	0.078	0.073	-0.065	0.221
	Equal variances not assumed			1.052	702.423	0.293	0.078	0.074	-0.067	0.223
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	3.784	0.052	-0.133	801	0.895	-0.009	0.069	-0.144	0.126
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.134	782.665	0.894	-0.009	0.068	-0.143	0.125
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.838	0.36	4.037	769	0	0.301	0.074	0.154	0.447
	Equal variances not assumed			3.981	661.745	0	0.301	0.075	0.152	0.449

Table 84: Comparing “Selecting a playlist to match my musical preferences” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.313	0.576	-2.643	803	0.008	-0.184	0.07	-0.321	0.047
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.64	765.864	0.008	-0.184	0.07	-0.321	0.047
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.01	0.92	-2.08	816	0.038	-0.149	0.071	-0.289	0.008
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.086	792.47	0.037	-0.149	0.071	-0.289	0.009
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.35	0.554	-0.786	806	0.432	-0.056	0.071	-0.195	0.083
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.781	735.977	0.435	-0.056	0.071	-0.195	0.084
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.994	0.319	-2.081	804	0.038	-0.144	0.069	-0.28	0.008
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.075	755.443	0.038	-0.144	0.069	-0.28	0.008
Paging	Equal variances assumed	5.396	0.02	-2.304	769	0.021	-0.169	0.073	-0.312	0.025
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.266	655.286	0.024	-0.169	0.074	-0.315	0.022

Table 85: Comparing “Selecting the best and most efficient route in my GPS navigation app while driving” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.227	0.634	-1.346	802	0.179	-0.095	0.07	-0.233	0.043
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.351	779.215	0.177	-0.095	0.07	-0.232	0.043
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.145	0.703	-1.2	816	0.231	-0.078	0.065	-0.206	0.05
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.199	778.95	0.231	-0.078	0.065	-0.206	0.05
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.11	0.74	-2.091	802	0.037	-0.138	0.066	-0.268	0.009
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.096	752.181	0.036	-0.138	0.066	-0.268	0.009
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	3.422	0.065	-2.644	804	0.008	-0.172	0.065	-0.299	0.044
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.671	787.229	0.008	-0.172	0.064	-0.298	0.045
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.23	0.632	-2.073	769	0.038	-0.132	0.063	-0.256	0.007
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.071	698.352	0.039	-0.132	0.064	-0.256	0.007

Table 86: Comparing “Autonomous driving of a motor vehicle” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.655	0.418	1.003	803	0.316	0.076	0.076	-0.073	0.225
	Equal variances not assumed				760.115	0.318	0.076	0.076	-0.073	0.225
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	1.691	0.194	-1.024	815	0.306	-0.077	0.075	-0.224	0.07
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.016	752.913	0.31	-0.077	0.076	-0.225	0.072
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	2.043	0.153	0.106	806	0.915	0.008	0.077	-0.142	0.158
	Equal variances not assumed			0.106	731.025	0.916	0.008	0.077	-0.143	0.16
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	1.69	0.194	-2.647	803	0.008	-0.195	0.074	-0.339	-0.05
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.622	730.283	0.009	-0.195	0.074	-0.34	-0.049
Paging	Equal variances assumed	1.693	0.194	-0.098	767	0.922	-0.007	0.077	-0.158	0.143
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.097	679.794	0.923	-0.007	0.077	-0.159	0.144

Table 87: Comparing “Diagnosis of my medical status by an AI system” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	6.34	0.012	-0.502	803	0.616	-0.037	0.073	-0.18	0.107
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.496	729.085	0.62	-0.037	0.074	-0.181	0.108
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.976	0.324	-0.836	818	0.403	-0.059	0.07	-0.197	0.079
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.832	769.297	0.406	-0.059	0.071	-0.198	0.08
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0	0.986	-0.961	804	0.337	-0.07	0.073	-0.214	0.074
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.957	741.144	0.339	-0.07	0.074	-0.215	0.074
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	5.948	0.015	-1.112	797	0.267	-0.079	0.071	-0.217	0.06
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.101	728.556	0.271	-0.079	0.071	-0.219	0.061
Paging	Equal variances assumed	3.564	0.059	-1.19	768	0.234	-0.085	0.071	-0.224	0.055
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.181	680.072	0.238	-0.085	0.072	-0.225	0.056

Table 88: Comparing “The variety and ease of online shopping sometimes leads me to make purchases that I later find unnecessary” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	3.114	0.078	-2.105	674	0.036	-0.198	0.094	-0.383	0.013
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.084	618.267	0.038	-0.198	0.095	-0.385	0.011
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.003	0.954	-1.37	682	0.171	-0.124	0.09	-0.301	0.054
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.368	653.883	0.172	-0.124	0.09	-0.301	0.054
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.148	0.7	-1.194	674	0.233	-0.103	0.087	-0.274	0.067
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.192	628.813	0.234	-0.103	0.087	-0.274	0.067
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	5.792	0.016	-4.1	662	0	-0.36	0.088	-0.532	0.187
	Equal variances not assumed			-4.102	642.68	0	-0.36	0.088	-0.532	0.187
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.457	0.499	-2.076	638	0.038	-0.191	0.092	-0.372	-0.01
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.077	578.576	0.038	-0.191	0.092	-0.372	-0.01

Table 89: Comparing “User ratings and reviews of products and services can be trusted” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	14.082	0	-1.303	673	0.193	-0.085	0.065	-0.213	0.043
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.281	593.214	0.201	-0.085	0.066	-0.215	0.045
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	4.945	0.026	-0.918	682	0.359	-0.058	0.063	-0.182	0.066
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.907	621.441	0.365	-0.058	0.064	-0.183	0.067
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.051	0.822	0.024	672	0.981	0.001	0.061	-0.117	0.12
	Equal variances not assumed			0.024	612.599	0.981	0.001	0.061	-0.118	0.121
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.594	0.441	-2.581	660	0.01	-0.158	0.061	-0.278	-0.038
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.606	656.908	0.009	-0.158	0.06	-0.276	-0.039
Paging	Equal variances assumed	5.143	0.024	-2.126	636	0.034	-0.138	0.065	-0.265	-0.011
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.112	557.74	0.035	-0.138	0.065	-0.266	-0.01

Table 90: Comparing “I prefer to tangibly test, see and "feel" the product that I buy” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0	0.986	1.48	813	0.139	0.105	0.071	-0.034	0.244
	Equal variances not assumed			1.479	783.143	0.14	0.105	0.071	-0.034	0.244
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	4.842	0.028	2.319	825	0.021	0.152	0.066	0.023	0.281
	Equal variances not assumed			2.287	738.43	0.023	0.152	0.067	0.022	0.283
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.499	0.48	1.345	819	0.179	0.092	0.069	-0.042	0.227
	Equal variances not assumed			1.35	780.778	0.177	0.092	0.068	-0.042	0.227
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.336	0.562	3.137	820	0.002	0.2	0.064	0.075	0.324
	Equal variances not assumed			3.104	743.681	0.002	0.2	0.064	0.073	0.326
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.847	0.358	-0.958	785	0.338	-0.067	0.07	-0.206	0.071
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.955	704.568	0.34	-0.067	0.071	-0.206	0.071

Table 91: Comparing “Long delivery times deter me from making an on-line purchase” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	1.235	0.267	-1.218	811	0.224	-0.095	0.078	-0.247	0.058
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.214	772.251	0.225	-0.095	0.078	-0.247	0.058
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	1.616	0.204	-0.529	825	0.597	-0.037	0.071	-0.176	0.101
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.526	777.911	0.599	-0.037	0.071	-0.177	0.102
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.05	0.823	-3.132	810	0.002	-0.228	0.073	-0.371	-0.085
	Equal variances not assumed			-3.158	783.21	0.002	-0.228	0.072	-0.37	-0.086
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	2.224	0.136	0.928	809	0.354	0.067	0.072	-0.075	0.208
	Equal variances not assumed			0.92	742.755	0.358	0.067	0.073	-0.076	0.21
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.393	0.531	-0.773	784	0.44	-0.057	0.073	-0.2	0.087
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.769	704.598	0.442	-0.057	0.073	-0.201	0.088

Table 92: Comparing “I have trust concerns about receiving or returning goods” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.001	0.978	0.402	810	0.688	0.03	0.074	-0.116	0.176
	Equal variances not assumed			0.402	774.773	0.688	0.03	0.075	-0.116	0.176
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.018	0.893	-0.939	824	0.348	-0.067	0.071	-0.207	0.073
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.939	789.662	0.348	-0.067	0.071	-0.207	0.073
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	3.493	0.062	-1.134	817	0.257	-0.082	0.072	-0.224	0.06
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.13	753.9	0.259	-0.082	0.073	-0.225	0.061
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.084	0.773	0.756	804	0.45	0.054	0.071	-0.086	0.194
	Equal variances not assumed			0.754	755.44	0.451	0.054	0.072	-0.086	0.194
Paging	Equal variances assumed	2.735	0.099	-0.095	782	0.924	-0.007	0.073	-0.149	0.135
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.094	682.978	0.925	-0.007	0.073	-0.151	0.137

Table 93: Comparing “I’m unable to buy online because I do not have a credit card” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	12.676	0	-1.635	807	0.102	-0.15	0.091	-0.329	0.03
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.618	738.859	0.106	-0.15	0.092	-0.331	0.032
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.341	0.559	-0.889	824	0.375	-0.078	0.087	-0.249	0.094
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.887	786.749	0.375	-0.078	0.087	-0.249	0.094
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	2.479	0.116	-1.473	813	0.141	-0.126	0.086	-0.295	0.042
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.458	731.494	0.145	-0.126	0.087	-0.297	0.044
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.504	0.478	-0.56	803	0.575	-0.049	0.087	-0.219	0.122
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.558	748.939	0.577	-0.049	0.087	-0.22	0.123
Paging	Equal variances assumed	7.311	0.007	-1.634	784	0.103	-0.138	0.084	-0.304	0.028
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.603	662.429	0.109	-0.138	0.086	-0.307	0.031

Table 94: Comparing “I am concerned about website security while shopping online” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.059	0.808	0.49	808	0.624	0.04	0.081	-0.119	0.198
	Equal variances not assumed			0.49	777.432	0.624	0.04	0.081	-0.119	0.198
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.39	0.532	0.61	824	0.542	0.045	0.074	-0.1	0.19
	Equal variances not assumed			0.609	786.11	0.543	0.045	0.074	-0.1	0.191
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	0.071	0.789	0.659	817	0.51	0.05	0.075	-0.098	0.198
	Equal variances not assumed			0.661	775.925	0.509	0.05	0.075	-0.098	0.197
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	2.383	0.123	1.076	802	0.282	0.076	0.07	-0.062	0.214
	Equal variances not assumed			1.077	764.432	0.282	0.076	0.07	-0.062	0.214
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.173	0.677	1.274	783	0.203	0.096	0.075	-0.052	0.244
	Equal variances not assumed			1.267	699.942	0.206	0.096	0.076	-0.053	0.245

Table 95: Comparing “I am concerned about the privacy of personal data while shopping online” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	0.262	0.609	-0.37	810	0.712	-0.028	0.077	-0.18	0.123
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.37	784.588	0.711	-0.028	0.077	-0.179	0.122
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.609	0.435	0.932	823	0.352	0.071	0.076	-0.078	0.219
	Equal variances not assumed			0.928	776.915	0.354	0.071	0.076	-0.079	0.22
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	4.491	0.034	-0.043	819	0.965	-0.003	0.075	-0.151	0.145
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.043	739.054	0.966	-0.003	0.076	-0.153	0.146
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.238	0.626	2.058	804	0.04	0.151	0.073	0.007	0.294
	Equal variances not assumed			2.055	761.05	0.04	0.151	0.073	0.007	0.295
Paging	Equal variances assumed	5.474	0.02	1.661	782	0.097	0.125	0.075	-0.023	0.272
	Equal variances not assumed			1.631	664.154	0.103	0.125	0.076	-0.025	0.274

Table 96: Comparing “I lack the necessary digital skills to shop online” between devices

Independent Samples Test										
Experimental cell		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Grid	Equal variances assumed	1.028	0.311	2.788	812	0.005	0.228	0.082	0.067	0.389
	Equal variances not assumed			2.79	785.74	0.005	0.228	0.082	0.068	0.389
Scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.993	0.319	0.064	824	0.949	0.005	0.08	-0.151	0.162
	Equal variances not assumed			0.063	781.276	0.949	0.005	0.08	-0.152	0.162
Unfolding	Equal variances assumed	1.033	0.31	-0.279	819	0.78	-0.023	0.083	-0.186	0.14
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.28	775.068	0.78	-0.023	0.083	-0.186	0.139
Horizontal scrolling	Equal variances assumed	0.001	0.972	0.548	801	0.584	0.046	0.084	-0.119	0.212
	Equal variances not assumed			0.549	767.674	0.583	0.046	0.084	-0.119	0.211
Paging	Equal variances assumed	0.013	0.908	1.391	783	0.165	0.115	0.083	-0.047	0.278
	Equal variances not assumed			1.388	710.868	0.166	0.115	0.083	-0.048	0.279